

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2
0
2
4

No 4

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

Yashil **IQTISODIYOT** **TARAQQIYOT** va

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Elektron nashr. 882 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 30-aprelda ruxsat etildi.

Muharrir:
Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, t.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, i.f.d., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri o'rinbosari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, i.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy Majlisi qonunchilik palatasi deputati
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich i.f.n., professor, MIM akademiyasi rektori
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, i.f.d., prof., TDIU YoMMMIB birinchi prorektori
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalendarovna, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo'yicha prorektori
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, i.f.d., prof., "O'IRIAM" ilmiy tadqiqot markazi direktori – prorektor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, i.f.d., TMI professori
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, i.f.n., TDIU professori
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, t.f.d., Rossiya xalqlar do'stligi universiteti professori
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, i.f.d., prof., Xalqaro "Nordik" universiteti rektori
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, f.f.d., TDIU professori
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, i.f.d. TDIU professori
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, t.f.d., profesor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Musyeva Shoira Azimovna, SamDu IS instituti professori
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, i.f.f.d., "El-yurt umidi" jamg'armasi ijrochi direktori o'rinbosari
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, t.f.f.d., TAQU katta o'qituvchisi
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, i. f. n., TDAU dotsenti
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, f.f.n., Farg'ona davlat universiteti dotsenti
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, i.f.f.d. (PhD), Alfraganus universiteti dotsenti
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, Turkiya Anqara universiteti doktoranti
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farxod, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi iqtisodiy jinoyatlarga qarshi kurashish departamenti bo'limi boshlig'i
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, i.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, i.f.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, i.f.d., TMI dotsenti
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

MUNDARIJA

Organizational Behavior and Leadership.....	10
Ibrokhim Gulomov	
Baliqchilikda klasterlarini tashkil etishning nazariy asoslari	18
Olim Murtazayev, Muydinov Olim Bekmurotovich	
Оценка состояния привлечения инвестиций в сферу туризма Узбекистана и механизмы управления	24
Арзиматов Бобирмирзо Зокирджон угли	
Biologik aktivlar buxgalteriya hisobni milliy va xalqaro standartlarga muvofiq takomillashtirish masalalari ...	27
Axmadaliyeva Zebo Abduxalimovna	
Aholi yashash joylarida yong'in risklarini bartaraf etish xizmatlardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari	32
Aziz Zikriyoev	
O'zbekistonda ilmiy darajali kadrlar tayyorlash tizimi boshqaruvining tashkiliy tuzilmasi va vazifalari.....	40
Beknaeva Shaxnoza Vladimirovna	
Mintaqaviy turizmning iqtisodiyot rivojlanishiga ta'siri (O'zbekiston turistik xizmatlar bozori misolida).....	45
D. B. O'roqova	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini ko'paytirishning asosiy yo'llari.....	50
Ibrohimov Boburmirro Baxtiyor o'g'li, Sayfiddinov Sarvarbek Anvarbek o'g'li	
Sanoat korxonalarining aksiyalar bozorida faoliyati tahlili: muammolar va yechimlar	55
Igitov Jurabek Kuzibekovich	
Qurilishda modernizatsiya va diversifikatsiya qilish asosida yangi ishlab chiqarish quvvatlarini oshirish	63
Islamov Ozodjon	
Sanoat korxonalarini innovatsion salohiyatini oshirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	67
J. K. Boymurodov	
Mamlakatda yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	72
Kadirxodjayeva Nilufar Raxmatullayevna	
BlokchEYn texnologiyalari yordamida raqamli iqtisodiyotni o'zgartirish	77
Karabayev Rustam Zafarovich, Saitkamolov Muxammadxo'ja Sobirxo'ja o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida zamonaviy mehnat bozorining rivojlanishi	84
Layli Mirzayeva	
Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini rivojlantirishda investitsion resurslardan samarali foydalanish mexanizmlari.....	88
Luiza Komilovna Xaydarova	
Umumta'lim muassasalari sonining ekonometrik tahlilini pedagogik metodlar yordamida amalga oshirish....	93
Ravshanova Muhayyo Maxmanazarovna	
O'zbekiston tarixiy shaharlarida turistik faoliyati shakllanishi va ularni boshqarishning nazariy asoslari.....	98
Meliqulov G'ayrat Abdug'afforovich	
Iqtisodiy rivojlanish va ilmiy tadqiqot rivojlanishining havo ifloslanish darajasiga ta'siri	105
Murodullayev Kamoliddin Sherzod o'g'li, Sadibekova Bibisora Djapparovna, Turdiqulov Farrux Ravshanjon o'g'li	
Hududlarni rivojlantirish va "yashil iqtisodiyot"ni shakllantirishning ekologik muammolari.....	110
Maxkamov Saidafzal Saidkamol o'g'li, Yigitaliyeva Dilnavo Mansurjon qizi	
Ekoturizm obyektining tasniflanishi va alohida xususiyatlari	116
Qodirov Azizjon Anvarovich	
Mamlakatimiz oliy ta'lim tizimida sifat menejmentidan foydalanishning konseptual asoslari	121
Saidqulova Furuza Farmonovna	
Bo'lajak iqtisodchilarning kasbiy kompetensiyalari.....	125
Shukurova Marifat Xodjiakbar qizi	
Ta'limning bosqichlari va ularning inson kapitalini shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati	129
To'rayeva Hurriyat To'yqulovna	

Hududlarda to'g'ridan to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etish dasturini amalga oshirishda marketingni rivojlantirish yo'llari	136
Xamidov O. X., Tojiyeva A. F.	
Investitsiyalar marketingining strategik aspektlari.....	143
Xodjamberdiyeva Dilnoza Bahtiyorovna	
Xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishda investitsion muhit jozibadorligini oshirishga nazariy qarashlar	149
A. Bektemirov, A. A. Abdurahmonov	
Qishloq xo'jaligi raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning ilg'or xorij tajribasi	154
Abdulloyev Asliddin Junaydullayevich, Ochilov Narzullo Fayzulloyevich	
Sanoat ishlab chiqarish tizimining investitsion xususiyatlari.....	159
Yodgorova Xalima To'liqinovna	
Turizm sohasi uchun yuqori malakali kadrlarni tayyorlashda davlat va xususiy sherikchilikning o'zaro bog'liqligi tahlili.....	165
Raxmatov Adxam Itolmasovich	
Mamlakatimizda turizm tashkilotlari faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlash maqsadida marketing instrumentlari orqali samarali tizim yaratish.....	169
Suyunova Kamilla Baxromovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligida agrokimyo xizmatlar ko'rsatishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari	173
Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich	
Yashil iqtisodiyotga investitsiyalarni jalb qilishni faollashtirish muammolari.....	178
Xomitov K. Z., Masharipova S. R.	
Considerations on the Problem of Illegal Migration and Human Trafficking	183
Azamatova Gulmira Bayirbekovna, Otarbayeva Guljan Kobeyevna	
Sustainable Development and Environmental Economics in Uzbekistan: A Focus on Carbon Pricing and Renewable Energy	186
Muhammadiyev Po'latjon Ilhomjon o'g'li, Urganbayeva Dilnoza Toxtasinovna	
The use of Digital Technologies in the Provision Of Utilities to the Population	192
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich, Inoyatova Durdona Shoxaydarovna, Alijonov Jamshid Alijon o'g'li	
The Current State of the Digital Economy in the Agrarian Sphere: Problems and Solutions	196
Babadjanov Abdirashid Musayevich	
Behavioral Theory of the Firm.....	201
Egamberdiyeva Oydin Abror qizi	
The Role of Information Technologies in Increasing the Capitalization of Commercial Banks	207
Egamova Makhfurat Esanovna	
Финансовые риски в исламском финансировании для внедрения в Республики Узбекистан	211
Абдуллоев Фуркат Олимджонович	
Совершенствование методологии экспертизы инвестиционных проектов	216
Бекимбетова Гулнора Маратовна	
Методические подходы к формированию механизмов стратегического управления развитием химической отрасли.....	223
Бибутова Шахло Саъдуллаевна	
Меры по снижению доли теневой экономики в стране.....	228
Махмудова Юлдузхон Бахромжон кизи, Сафаров Гиёсиддин Абдуллаевич ўгли	
Формирование национальной инновационной системы – одна из приоритетных задач повышения конкурентоспособности Республики Узбекистан	232
Н. М. Махмудов, А. А. Алиев, З. А. Мирзоев	
Мониторинг и анализ современного состояния и развития промышленности в Узбекистане.....	237
Назарова Раъно Рустамовна, Исмоилова Малика Дилшодовна	
Цифровая платформа как инструмент трансформации бизнес-процессов.....	243
Раупов Жамшид Рашидович	
Роль применения ключевых показателей эффективности труда на предприятиях.....	249
Рахматуллаева Шахноза Хамидовна	

Влияние цифровой трансформации на инвестиционную привлекательность Узбекистана.....	255
Саиткамоллов Муҳаммадхожа Сабирходжа угли, Маркабаева Жансая Айбек кызы	
Организация и координация методической помощи при управлении педагогическими кадрами	261
Хакимова Майя Юрьевна	
Интеграция узбекистана в мировое экономическое содружество путем унификации бухгалтерского учета на основе МСФО	266
Зарипова Саёхат Зафаровна	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan investitsiya loyihalarini moliyalashni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari.....	271
Abduqodirova Ozoda Anvarjon qizi	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan jismoniy shaxslarga ajratilgan kreditlarning joriy tahlili.....	276
Abdusalomov Jaxongir O'ktam o'g'li	
Globalashuv sharoitida mamlakatimizda sug'urta bozorini raqamlashtirishning ahamiyati	282
Anvarova Z.	
The Role of Parents and Teachers in Promoting a Healthy Lifestyle in Children.....	286
Axtamov Djamshed Baxromovich	
A Study of the Importance of Green Economy in Uzbekistan Sustainable Economic Development and its Measurement Indicators in Relation to Environment.....	291
Ataniyazova Maksuda Baltayevna, Tairova Zarnigor Mammot qizi	
Konsolidatsiyalashgan moliyaviy hisobot tuzishning zarurligi.....	296
Avazov Iloxom Ravshanovich	
Foydani soliqqa tortish obyekti sifatidagi iqtisodiy tarkibi.....	301
Axrorov Zarif Oripovich	
Surxondaryo viloyatida aholining uy-joy bilan ta'minlanganlik darajasini tahlili.....	309
Ibragimov Qobil To'xtamishovich	
Review of Methodological Approaches to Enterprises Financial Condition Analysis.....	314
Ismailova Maxbuba Mirxalilovna	
Innovatsion rivojlanish sharoitida xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini tasniflanishining nazariy va ilmiy asoslari.....	319
Masharipova Manzura Alimbayevna	
Korxonalarda benchmarking strategiyalarini qo'llashning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlari.....	325
Narziyeva Dilafiruz Muxtorovna	
Davlat budjetining soliqsiz daromadlari shakllanishini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	330
O'ktamova Nargiza Narzulla qizi	
Mamlakatimizda sanoat ishlab chiqarishi korxonalarining rivojlanish holati tahlili.....	334
Olimov Maqsudjon Komiljon o'g'li	
Moliyaviy natijalar to'g'risidagi hisobotni moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlar talablari asosida tuzish.....	339
Pardayeva Zulfizar Alimovna	
Raqamlashtirish sharoitida qo'shma korxonasi faoliyatining tahlili.....	343
Rashidov Jamshid Xamidovich	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning rivojlanishida oilaviy tadbirkorlikning o'rni.....	348
Raximov Baxromjon Ibroximovich, Saloxiddinov Zuxriddin Nuriddin o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida xizmat ko'rsatishning ilmiy asoslari.....	352
Suyunov Asror Baxtiyorovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida telekommunikatsiya sohasini rivojlantirish ilmiy asoslari.....	356
Toshmatov Salohiddin Zayniddinovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida innovatsiyalarni joriy etishning huquqiy masalalari.....	360
Turg'unov Saloxiddin Jamol o'g'li, Mirzayeva Mohidil Vohidovna	
Zamonaviy sharoitlarda korxonalarining moliyaviy baqarorligini yaxshilash masalalari	366
Usmanova Guljahon Ulug'bek qizi	
Franshizalarni jalb qilishda davlat boshqaruvi tizimida marketing tadqiqotlarining ahamiyati	371
Xodjayev Anvar Rasulovich	

Transport Decarbonization Strategy.....	377
Yarashova Vasila Kamalovna, Muradov Bekzod Xidirnazar ugli	
Temir yo'l transportida ishlab chiqarish faoliyatining iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish	382
Yermatova Dilnoza Axmadjonovna	
Iqtisodiyotda davlat ishtirokini qisqartirish va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish istiqbollari	387
Yuldashev Xusniddin Abdullayevich	
Issiqlik ta'minoti xizmatlarini ko'rsatish samaradorligi va sifatini baholash ko'rsatkichlari tizimi.....	390
Abdulaziz Abdumo'minovich Matro'ziyev	
Issiqlik ta'minoti xizmatlari sifatiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar va ularni baholash	394
Abdulaziz Abdumo'minovich Matro'ziyev	
Jismoniy shaxslarning mol-mulkiga soliq solishni takomillashtirish.....	399
Abdullayev Zafarjon Alijonovich, Zaydullayev Abduhabib Boliqul o'g'li	
Sug'urta tashkilotlarida hisob siyosatini ishlab chiqishning ahamiyati.....	404
Abduraimova Maftunaxon Axmatovna	
Bank risklarini boshqarishning xalqaro tajribalari.....	409
Abdurasulov Jaxongir Abduvaliyevich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlari ijtimoiy ma'sulligini ta'minlash mexanizmining amal qilish darajasi.....	416
Bayisbayev Javlon Nurlanovich	
Qishloq aholisining qishloq xo'jaligida bilim va innovatsiyalarni o'zlashtirishga ta'sir etuvchi omillarni iqtisodiy baholash (Samarqand viloyati misolida).....	421
Bozorova Lobar Nuralevna	
Направления совершенствования инновационных стратегий в деятельности промышленных предприятий.....	427
Дониерова Зухрабону Алишер кизи	
Mol-mulk solig'ining korxonalar faoliyatiga ta'siri.....	432
Qudiyarov Kishibay Ramatullayevich	
Banklar reytingini aniqlash va barqarorligini ta'minlashning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	438
Maxmudov Omon Tuxtayevich	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida tijorat banklarining aktiv va passiv operatsiyalarini innovatsion usullar orqali boshqarishni takomillashtirish	442
Mo'minova Ma'suda Baxtiyarovna	
Auditorlik tekshiruvini dasturiy ta'minot asosida tashkil etish: muammo va yechimlar.....	447
Nazarova Kamola Sattoral qizi	
Ishlab chiqarish infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishning davlat tomonidan tartibga solish konsepsiyasi.....	453
Normurodov Xusan Eshmaxmatovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning ahamiyati hamda uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	460
Nurullayeva Shaxnoza, Saydullayeva Saodat	
Tijorat banklari inson kapitali samaradorligini baholashda KPI ko'rsatkichlaridan foydalanish mexanizmlari	467
Turaeva Mastura Kurbanovna	
Сущность и особенности инвестиционно-строительного процесса	471
А. Бектемиров, Б.М.Абдувалиев	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlarni boshqarishning dolzarb masalalari.....	478
Saidov Hayotjon Raxmatulloevich	
Tijorat banklarida kredit operatsiyalari hisobini takomillashtirish.....	482
Sa'dullayeva Asalxon Muzaffarovna	
Ko'p tarmoqli fermer xo'jaliklarining raqobatbardoshlikni baholash usullari	485
Abdulloyev Asliddin Junaydullayevich, Teshayev Mirolim Djumayevich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarida soliq yukini optimallashtirish mexanizmi	490
To'xsanov Quدراتillo Nozimovich	

Davlat sektorida ichki audit tadbirlarini umumiy rejalashtirish	495
Xamidova Z. U.	
Aholi moliyaviy savodxonligini oshirish va uning ahamiyati.....	501
Xudayarova Xurshida Abdunazarovna	
Kambag'allikni qisqartirishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	505
Xudoyberdiyev Jamshid Juraboy o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida buxgalteriya hisobi va ichki auditni takomillashtirish	511
Shaymatova Nargiza Ashurovna	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida sug'urta xizmatlari.....	516
Shodmonova Odina G'ofur qizi	
Fuqarolar davlat pensiya ta'minoti tizimining amaldagi holati tahlili.....	520
Sholdarov Dilshod Azimiddin o'g'li	
Aholiga bank xizmatlari ko'rsatishning ijtimoiy ahamiyati.....	525
Eldor Uskanov	
Innovatsion boshqaruvning ilg'or xorijiy tajribalari	530
Yusupova Jamila Karamatdinovna	
Neft-gaz korxonalarini moliyaviy-iqtisodiy faoliyati natijalari tahlili ("O'ZBEKNEFTGAZ" AJ misolida)	534
Umurzoqov Jamoliddin Sherbekovich	
Korxonalarda savdo marketing faoliyati samaradorligini baholash.....	541
Sobirov Azizbek Avzbekovich	
Moliyaviy firibgarliklarga qarshi kurashishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	548
Gadaev Ismat Yadgarovich	
Hududlarda islom iqtisodiyoti tamoyillari asosida amalga oshirilgan investitsion loyihalar: to'siqlar va yechimlar	551
Irgasheva Gulbahor Sodiqovna	
O'zbekistonda investitsiyalardan samarali foydalanish asosida oziq-ovqat sanoati samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	554
Kobilova Nasiba Xurramovna	
Foreign Economic Relations as a Factor of Effective Functioning of the Economy	561
Bakhodurova Sulkhya Azizkhodjaevna, Li Marina Rudolfovna, Mukhtarova Donata Ravshanbekovna, Romashkin Roman Anatolyevich	
Modern Approaches to the Organization and Development of the Consumer Services Market.....	566
Musyeva Shoira Azimovna	
Ishlab chiqarish siklini qisqartirishning iqtisodiy samaradorligi.....	570
Odina Nabiyevna Tuychiyeva, Nazarova Latofat Toirjon qizi	
Asalarichilik mahsulotlari bozorida marketing strategiyasini amalga oshirish.....	575
Rashidova Xadicha Tursunalievna	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida bank faoliyatini iqtisodiy-matematik modellashtirish yo'llari	581
Raxmanov Mexridin Sindarovich	
Korporativ boshqaruv amaliyoti bo'yicha hisobot tuzish bo'yicha xorijiy tajriba.....	586
Tashmatov Rustam Xusanovich	
Iqtisodiyotda davlat ishtirokini qisqartirish va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish istiqbollari	592
Yuldashev Xusniddin Abdullayevich	
Iqtisodiyotda turizm o'rnini statistik baholash uslubiyoti.....	595
Zilola Jumanova	
Финансовые риски в исламском финансировании для внедрения в Республики Узбекистан	602
Абдуллоев Фуркат Олимджонович	
Блокчейн-технология и информационная безопасность в цифровой экономике Узбекистана.....	607
Кадиров Алишер Исмаилович	
Цифровая платформа как инструмент трансформации бизнес-процессов	611
Раупов Жамшид Рашидович	

O'zbekistonda zamonaviy kabel va sim mahsulotlari ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonalar faoliyatiga nazar.....	617
Rashidova Odina Olimjon qizi	
Современные тенденции развития валютных отношений в Узбекистане	622
Камалов Камолалдин Кахрамонович	
Sug'urta sohasining O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotidagi o'rni	626
Sharobiddinov Akramjon Goyibbayevich	
Kichik biznes va tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning xorij tajribasi va undan O'zbekistonda foydalanish yo'nalishlari	630
Fayziyeva Aziza Azamat qizi	
Modeling the Stackelberg strategy in a linear model (linear city) Hotteling.....	635
Musayeva Shaira Azimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
Mulkning kapitallashuvi darajasini iqtisodiy jihatdan amalga oshirish samaradorligini baholash uslublari.....	644
Norboyev Odil Abrayevich	
Tijorat banklarining kredit portfelini amaliy holati va ekonometrik tahlillari: ATB "Aloqabank" misolida.....	649
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich, Norova Nozima Nabiyeвна	
O'zbekistonda "yashil iqtisodiyot" muhitida kreditlash va moliyalashtirish imkoniyatlari	654
Taxir Urkinbayev	
Budjet tashkilotlarida ichki nazorat tizimini tashkil qilishning xususiyatlari.....	658
Abduraxmanov Ramazon Abdullayevich	
Chinese Commercial Banks Experience in Asset Diversification	663
Uktamova Nozima Narzulla kizi	
Sanoat taraqqiyotida ishlab chiqarish korxonalarini ustuvor rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	667
Yadgarov Akram Akbarovich	
Анализ деятельности коммерческих банков Узбекистана по кредитованию физических лиц.....	673
Базарова Нигора Равшановна	
Mahalliy va xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishning innovatsion jarayonlarga ta'sirini baholash.....	684
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida innovatsiyalarning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari	689
Kuziyeva Nargiza Ramazanovna, Xusanov Faxriddin Jamoliddin o'g'li	
Tashqi mehnat migratsiyasi.....	694
O. N. Djurayev	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda sanoat tarmog'ining davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanishini baholash	699
Otaboyeva Dildora	
Nobank kredit tashkilotlarining moliyaviy xizmatlari sifatini oshirishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi	705
Raimov Xurshid Muxtorovich	
Tijorat banklarida moliyaviy injiniringni qo'llash istiqbollari	711
Saipnazarov Sherbek Shaylavbekovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi moliya bozorida tijorat banklari faoliyati: muammo va yechimlar	716
Toymuxamedov Ibroxim Rixsiboevich, Jumaev Islombek Akram o'g'li	
Agrar ta'lim tizimida boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari	723
Boltayev Nurali Shiramatovich, Beglayev Uchqun Xurramovich, Abdiyev Izzat Risqiboyevich	
O'zini o'zi band qilgan shaxslardan olinadigan soliqlarni takomillashtirish orqali yashirin iqtisodiyotni jilovlash masalalari	731
Davranov Iskandar Jumayevich	
Iqtisodiy konsentratsiyalarni tartibga solish va nazorat qilishni takomillashtirish.....	738
Luqmanov Sharifxon A'zam o'g'li	
Role of Private and Public Kindergartens in Early Childhood Development	744
Makhmudova Munisakhon Abbos qizi	
"Yashil" enegriya quvvatlarini barpo etish iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlash asosi sifatida.....	749
Muminova Elnoraxon Abdukarimovna, Umarova Dilnoza Oybek qizi	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda CVP-tahlilni tashkil etishning muammoli jihatlari	754
Qlichev Baxtiyor Pardayevich	

Korxonada likvidlik riskini minimallashtirish orqali uning moliyaviy barqarorligini saqlab qolish	759
Latipova Shaxnoza Maxmudovna	
Развитие международных торгово-экономических связей Республики Узбекистан	766
Ким Татьяна Валерьевна, Гофуржонова Шахрибону Бахромжон кизи	
Kapital qurilishni boshqarish samaradorligini oshirishning dolzarb masalalari	774
A. Bektemirov, M. U. Sarimsoqov	
O'zbekiston mehnat bozorida yoshlarning ish bilan bandlik darajasini oshirish.....	780
Mambetjanov Qahramon Qurbandurdiyevich, Bahromov Shahzod Fazliddinovich	
Роль имиджа в улучшении инвестиционной привлекательности высших учебных заведений.....	787
Жанзаков Бекзот, Жонузоков Мирзабек	
Innovatsion kichik tadbirkorlikni qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yicha xorij tajribasi va uni mamlakat iqtisodiyotida qo'llash imkoniyati.....	795
Toshaliyeva Saodat Toxirovna, Eshqulova Dilorom Abduravupovna	
Перспективы развития банковского сектора в Узбекистане для иностранных туристов	802
Муминов Шахзод Низомиддинович, Каримова Азиза Махомадризоевна	
Innovatsion faoliyat moliyaviy modellari va mexanizmlarini rivojlantirishning konseptual asoslari	806
Ruzibayeva Nargiza Xakimovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligi tarmoqlarini innovatsion rivojlantirish bo'yicha xorijiy tajribalar va ulardan respublikamizda samarali foydalanish yo'llari	814
Ishniyazov Baxrom Normamatovich	
Turistik xizmatlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va marketing tadqiqotlari.....	819
Berdiqulova Iroda Rayimqulovna	
Qoraqalpog'iston qishloq xo'jaligi: asosiy muammolar va rivojlanishining ustuvor yo'nalishlari	823
Yeshimbetov Uktamjon Xudaybergenovich	
Iqtisodiyotning erkinlashtirilishi sharoitlarida kichik biznes sektori rivojlanishining imkoniyatlari.....	832
Botirova R. A., Sirojiddinov I. Q.	
Kriptoalyuta va blokcheyn tadqiqotlari: tendensiyalar va istiqbollar	835
Berdiqulov Jurabek	
Bank risklarni monitoring qilish tizimini takomillashtirish	837
Hamroyev Sherzod Axtamovich	
O'zbekiston hududlariga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda ko'p qavatli "yashil" fermer xo'jaliklarini tashkil etishning ahamiyati	843
Turdimuratova Aziza Alisherovna	
Surxondaryo viloyatining mahalliy budjet daromadlarini oshirish yo'llari va uni arima modeli asosida prognozlash.....	846
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norqo'chqor qizi	
Qishloq xo'jaligi tarmog'ining mamlakat iqtisodiyotidagi o'rni va undagi tarkibiy o'zgarishlarni statistik baholash.....	856
Zakirova Umida Maxamadaminovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy mohiyati	863
Pardayev Jamshid Muzaffarovich	
Turizm bozorini rivojlantirishda mehnat bozorining tutgan o'rni va ahamiyati	872
Berdiqulova Iroda Rayimqulovna, Berdikulov Jurabek	
Проблемы расчета определения и планирования прибыли предприятий в условиях модернизации экономики	876
Алиева С.С.	

CHINESE COMMERCIAL BANKS EXPERIENCE IN ASSET DIVERSIFICATION

Uktamova Nozima Narzulla kizi

Ph.D., Tashkent State University of Law, Senior teacher of the "Public Administration" department

Abstract: Diversification is an important strategy for banks to remain competitive. Recent studies show that relative capital is considered an important determinant of bank competitiveness. The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of diversity and relational capital on the performance of Chinese commercial banks.

Key words: commercial banks, ROA, ROE, diversification, banks assets, HHI, capital.

Annotatsiya: Diversifikatsiya banklarning raqobatbardoshligini saqlab qolish uchun muhim strategiya hisoblanadi. So'nggi tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, nisbiy kapital bank raqobatbardoshligining muhim omili hisoblanadi. Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi xilma-xillik va nisbiy kapitalning Xitoy tijorat banklari faoliyatiga ta'sirini o'rganishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: tijorat banklari, ROA, ROE, diversifikatsiya, bank aktivlari, HHI, kapital.

Аннотация: Диверсификация является важной стратегией сохранения конкурентоспособности банков. Недавние исследования показывают, что относительный капитал считается важным фактором, определяющим конкурентоспособность банков. Целью данного исследования является изучение влияния разнообразия и реляционного капитала на эффективность китайских коммерческих банков.

Ключевые слова: коммерческие банки, ROA, ROE, диверсификация, активы банков, HHI, капитал.

INTRODUCTION

Since its entry into the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 2000, the Chinese government has pursued liberalization policies that allow foreign financial institutions to participate in domestic financial markets. In recent years, the Chinese government has implemented a number of financial policy reforms aimed at strengthening the financial system. These reforms include raising interest rates and eliminating the loan-to-deposit ratio. In light of dynamic financial markets, commercial banks should use this opportunity to expand their banking operations. Conversely, banks can earn significant profits from normal banking activities as a result of intense market competition.

In order to improve operational sustainability and growth, Chinese commercial banks are seeking to expand their banking activities, particularly by incorporating asset management activities into their banking portfolios to generate profits. Commercial banks engage in risk-free or low-risk businesses such as underwriting mutual funds and government bonds and marketing insurance products.

Businesses must develop and maintain partnership capital to win customer and brand loyalty, satisfaction, market image, goodwill, negotiating power and strategic partnerships. Gaughan, Duran, and Draghici (2014) believe that relative capital is one of the factors that determine bank competitiveness¹. Within the knowledge economy, relationship capital includes all intangible assets associated with external stakeholders. It serves as an important driver of competitive advantage, ultimately influencing the performance and value of organizations. Thus, the relative capital of commercial banks significantly affects competitiveness in the market, especially in terms of developing customer relationships and promoting financial products in the market.

Previous empirical studies show that diversification affects firm performance. The study aims to address the research gap by examining the impact of diversity and interconnected capital on the performance of Chinese commercial banks.

¹ Gogan, M. L., Duran, D. C., & Graghici, A. (2014). The impact of relational capital on competitiveness of organizations. *Network Intelligence Studies*, 2(2), 233-240.

Diversification is a critical business strategy for commercial banks to increase profitability and reduce risk. Non-interest earning activities refer to various banking services that are not affected by interest rates. These services include low or no risk financial activities such as foreign exchange trading and remittance transactions, as well as higher risk financial activities such as letter of credit, letter of guarantee, commercial bill guarantee, banker's acceptance and forward foreign exchange transactions. In addition, commercial banks also act as intermediaries in the sale of insurance products for the insurance business and mutual fund products for the securities investment sector to earn brokerage fees and commissions.

Previous studies have shown that the presence of non-interest income or diversification of bank income has a beneficial effect on bank performance. In addition, the study categorizes the banks included in the sample into five different banking groups: bank holding companies, commercial banks, cooperative banks, investment banks and savings banks. The non-interest income of a cooperative bank has a positive impact on the bank's profitability (ROA), while the non-interest income of a savings bank has a negative impact on the bank's profitability (ROA). In addition, investment banks' income from sources other than interest has a beneficial effect on banks' profitability, as measured by return on assets (ROA)². Ferreira, Zanini, and Alves (2019) used a data set consisting of 1019 observations from several types of Brazilian banks, including commercial banks, investment banks, and development banks, over the period 2003–2014. They use panel data methods to study the impact of bank income diversification on both risk and return. Empirical evidence shows that there is a positive correlation between a bank's non-interested income (NII), income concentration (HHI) and company performance (ROA)³.

Figure 1: Largest banks in the world as of December 2022 by assets ⁴

2 Lee, C.C, Yang, S. J, and Chang, C.H. (2014). Non-interest income, profitability, risk in banking industry: A cross-country analysis. *North American Journal of Economic and finance*, 17, 48 -67.

3 Ferreira, J.H.L, Zanini, F.A.M. and Alves, T.W., Bamnk. (2019). revenue diversification: Its impact on its risk and return in Brazilian banks. *Accounting and Finance Review*, 30(79), 91-106.

4 <https://www.statista.com/statistics/269845/largest-banks-in-the-world-by-total-assets/>

Further, in the course of the study, the following hypothesis is put forward.

1. Diversification has a positive effect on the bank's performance. Kale et al. (2000) believe that relational capital involves the level of mutual trust, respect and friendship that arises from close interactions between internal and external partners and is the core theme of relational capital⁵.

Chen et al (2004) define relational capital. as an intangible asset based on developing, maintaining and developing high quality relationships with any organization, individual or group that affects the business, including customers, suppliers, employees, government, partners, competitors and any other stakeholders⁶ De Clercq and Sapienza (2006) define relational capital as the extent to which the exchange involves trust, social interaction, and shared norms or goals. In other words, the key issue in achieving competitiveness is the ability to convert these intangible assets into value and use this value in the market⁷.

2. The combination of relational capital and diversification has a beneficial effect on bank performance.
3. The relationship between relative capital and diversification has a U-shaped effect on bank performance.

The Chinese banking system truly has the largest banks in the world in terms of banking assets. These banks include Industrial and Commercial Bank of China (ICBC), China Construction Bank, Agricultural Bank of China and Bank of China. They are key players not only in the Chinese market, but also have significant influence on the global economy due to their scale and large customer base.

Item	2023			2022		
	Average balance	Interest income/expense	Average yield/cost (%)	Average balance	Interest income/expense	Average yield/cost (%)
Assets						
Loans and advances to customers	25,006,605	951,845	3.81	22,246,265	900,063	4.05
Investment	10,266,019	338,267	3.30	8,975,046	297,106	3.31
Due from central banks ⁽²⁾	3,230,841	53,815	1.67	2,991,645	45,425	1.52
Due from banks and other financial institutions ⁽³⁾	2,172,554	61,112	2.81	1,867,047	36,080	1.93
Total interest-generating assets	40,676,019	1,405,039	3.45	36,080,003	1,278,674	3.54
Non-interest-generating assets	2,510,696			2,549,781		
Allowance for impairment losses on assets	(776,831)			(682,871)		
Total assets	42,409,884			37,946,913		
Liabilities						
Deposits	31,141,446	589,688	1.89	27,364,627	480,083	1.75
Due to banks and other financial institutions ⁽⁴⁾	4,058,487	103,529	2.55	3,794,532	70,732	1.86
Debt securities and certificates of deposit issued	1,508,148	56,809	3.77	1,132,767	35,874	3.17
Total interest-bearing liabilities	36,708,081	750,026	2.04	32,291,926	586,689	1.82
Non-interest-bearing liabilities	2,065,143			2,029,137		
Total liabilities	38,773,224			34,321,063		
Net interest income		655,013			691,985	
Net interest spread			1.41			1.72
Net interest margin			1.61			1.92

Figure 2: Average return on interest-bearing assets and average cost of interest-bearing liabilities ⁸

If we analyze 2023, Industrial and Commercial Bank of China (ICBC) has achieved a significant improvement in the quality of development. The Bank's return on investment, return on profit margin and cost to income ratio were 0.87%, 10.66% and 28.28% respectively, these figures are relatively good, indicating the effective

5 Kale, p, Singh, H. (2000). Learning and protection of proprietary assets in strategical alliances: Building relational capital. Strategic Management Journal, 21, 217-317.

6 Chen, J., Zhue, Z. and Zie, H.Y. (2004). Measuring intellectual capital: a new model and empirical study. Journal of Intellectual Capital, 5(1), 195-212

7 De Clercq, D., & Sapienza, H. J. (2006). Effects of relational capital and commitment on venture capitalists' perception of portfolio company performance. Journal of Business Venturing, 21, 326 -347.

8 INDUSTRIAL AND COMMERCIAL BANK OF CHINA LIMITED. Annual report 2023.

management of the bank. The bank achieved significant quantitative growth. Net profit rose to 365.1 billion yuan, and assets, deposits and loans increased by more than 10%, reaching a record level, demonstrating the bank's successful performance and ability to attract and retain customers. One of the bank's important achievements is the successful prevention and control of risks. The non-performing loan ratio decreased by 2 bps. to 1.36%, the provision for non-performing loans increased to 213.97%, and the capital adequacy ratio reached 19.10%, remaining at a relatively high level.

Overall, the results for 2023 indicate the bank's successful performance, its financial stability and ability to adapt to changing market conditions.

CONCLUSION

Asset diversification is a vital strategy for developed countries' commercial banks to manage risk, optimize returns, and gain a competitive edge in financial markets. Through a thorough review of various asset diversification strategies, it is evident that these banks face unique challenges but also reap substantial benefits. By diversifying their assets across different classes and regions, banks can mitigate risks associated with economic fluctuations and sector-specific crises. Additionally, diversification enables banks to optimize returns by capitalizing on varying market conditions and opportunities. Overall, asset diversification plays a crucial role in enhancing the resilience and profitability of developed countries' commercial banks in an increasingly complex and dynamic financial landscape.

References:

1. Gogan, M. L., Duran, D. C., & Graghici, A. (2014). The impact of relational capital on competitiveness of organizations. *Network Intelligence Studies*, 2(2), 233-240.
2. Lee, C.C, Yang, S. J, and Chang, C.H. (2014). Non-interest income, profitability, risk in banking industry: A cross-country analysis. *North American Journal of Economic and finance*, 17, 48 -67.
3. Ferreira, J.H.L, Zanini, F.A.M. and Alves, T.W., Bamnk. (2019). revenue diversification: Its impact on its risk and return in Brazilian banks. *Accounting and Finance Review*, 30(79), 91-106.
4. Kale, p, Singh, H. (2000). Learning and protection of proprietary assets in strategical alliances: Building relational capital. *Strategic Management Journal*,21, 217-317.
5. Chen, J., Zhue, Z. and Zie, H.Y. (2004). Measuring intellectual capital: a new model and empirical study. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 5(1), 195-212
6. De Clercq, D., & Sapienza, H. J. (2006). Effects of relational capital and commitment on venture capitalists' perception of portfolio company performance. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 21, 326 -347.
7. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/269845/largest-banks-in-the-world-by-total-assets/>
8. INDUSTRIAL AND COMMERCIAL BANK OF CHINA LIMITED. Annual report 2023.

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Xondamir Ismoilov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2024. № 4

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.

Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77)

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77) telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

